
NETWORK TRAFFIC FOUNDATION MODELS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Network Traffic Foundation Models (NT-FMs) aim to enable a “train-once, adapt-anywhere” paradigm for automated traffic management, yet current research remains fragmented. This systematic literature review analyses 51 primary studies published between 2017 and 2025. To evaluate the feasibility of developing NT-FMs, we address 4 research questions: (RQ1) we map prevailing AI architectures and their training regimes, including self-supervised pretraining objectives; (RQ2) we assess how network traffic is represented for input to NT-FMs; (RQ3) we examine the network environments and tasks to which NT-FMs have been applied; and (RQ4) we survey publicly available datasets suitable for training NT-FMs. Our content and bibliometric analyses indicate a rapidly expanding body of work, yet cross-task transfer remains limited; terabyte-scale corpora are scarce; and efficiency techniques are only beginning to emerge. Taken together, these findings indicate that NT-FM development is feasible but currently constrained by data scale and transfer limitations. We distil open challenges and propose a research agenda aimed at scalable, robust, and reliable NT-FMs.

Keywords Network Traffic · Foundation Models · Pretraining · Fine-tuning · Self-supervised Learning · Transformer · Network Management · Network Security

1 Introduction

In contemporary networks, the automatic management of traffic is vital to ensure performance, reliability, and security. Emerging technologies such as 5G/6G cellular networks, massive Internet of Things (IoT) deployments, and nascent quantum communications amplify traffic diversity and performance demands, further stressing traditional management approaches [1–3]. Manual configuration and ad-hoc rule-based systems struggle to keep pace with ever-growing volumes of traffic, rising application diversity and increasingly sophisticated threats.

Machine Learning (ML), and in particular Deep Learning (DL), has been applied extensively to network traffic analysis over the past decade [4]. Although early ML-based methods relied on handcrafted statistical features for tasks such as traffic classification and anomaly detection, more recent work exploits end-to-end models that learn directly from raw packet bytes. While these approaches deliver strong task-specific performance, they generally require large labelled datasets and must be retrained from scratch for each new task or environment [5].

In this context, Network Traffic Foundation Models (NT-FMs) are emerging as a new paradigm in network management and security research. These models aim to learn generalisable representations of network traffic by capturing fundamental patterns, structures, and semantics directly from large volumes of unlabelled traffic data, without being tied to any single downstream task. By pretraining once on diverse packet or flow traces and subsequently fine-tuning with minimal additional data, NT-FMs promise to streamline solutions across traffic classification, anomaly detection, performance prediction, traffic generation, and beyond [6] (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Four main types of network traffic analysis approaches: (a) Plaintext feature based fingerprint matching. (b) Statistical feature based ML. (c) Raw traffic feature based ML. (d) Raw traffic based pretraining & fine-tuning (NT-FMs approach). *Source:* [7]

The motivation for NT-FMs arises from three observations [8]. Traditional task-specific models for network traffic require a substantial amount of labelled data and bespoke engineering for each new protocol, topology, or environment. Moreover, many networking tasks share common underlying primitives that could be captured once and reused, such as temporal traffic bursts, protocol semantics, and traffic composition hierarchies. Additionally, large unlabelled datasets are routinely collected in operational networks, offering the raw material for self-supervised representation learning.

Foundation models were popularized by the Stanford Institute for Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence (HAI) in 2021 [9]. They made their first mark in Natural Language Processing (NLP), where they consistently outperformed earlier methods. This shift was catalysed by the publication of the Transformer architecture in 2017 [10], whose novel attention mechanism and pretraining on massive, unlabelled text corpora set a new standard. Building on that breakthrough, we’ve entered the era of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as OpenAI o3 [11], GPT-4o [12], Gemini 2.5 Pro [13], and Llama 4 [14]. Beyond NLP, the same pretrain-and-fine-tune paradigm has been successfully applied to Computer Vision (CV) [15], audio [16], and video [17] processing, and even to network traffic modelling and management, yielding similarly impressive gains.

Inspired by successes in other fields, NT-FMs adopt a similar approach. Instead of taking word tokens as input, they take data such as sequences of packet headers, payload fragments, flow statistics, and graph-based representations. As opposed to deriving linguistic meaning from the input, they learn “traffic semantics” from the interplay of protocols, application signatures, congestion behaviours, and security anomalies.

Early NT-FM prototypes have begun to appear. Some use packet-level tokenization and Transformer encoders to pretrain on unlabelled raw bytes and then fine-tune for classification tasks [7, 18]. Others employ graph neural network architectures to capture flow-level dynamics [19]. Another method involves others train autoencoder-style models to synthesise realistic traffic for simulation [20]. These efforts demonstrate NT-FMs’ potential to reduce labelling costs, improve cross-environment generalisation and unify multiple networking functions under a single representation.

In the context of this research trend in ML-based network traffic management, this work proposes a **systematic literature review that surveys the state of NT-FM research**, exploring intriguing directions. During this process, we have collected 51 relevant works encompassing diverse model architectures (e.g. Transformers, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), Autoencoders), pretraining objectives (e.g. masked prediction, link prediction), input representations (bytes, bursts, graphs), and application domains. Our analysis assesses the comparative strengths of different architectures and investigates how self-supervised objectives influence the representations learned by NT-FMs. It also explores the design trade-offs in packet-, burst-, and flow-level encodings. Moreover, it examines the range of applications—spanning classification, anomaly detection, and traffic synthesis—and evaluates the availability and adequacy of public traffic corpora required for truly large-scale, generalisable pretraining.

Contributions. The main contributions of this review are:

- **Comprehensive mapping of the state of the art.** We perform, to the best of our knowledge, the first systematic literature review devoted exclusively to NT-FMs. We retrieved, screened and analysed a corpus of 51 primary studies published between 2017–2025, thereby providing a consolidated reference for a rapidly fragmenting research landscape.
- **Four-dimensional analysis** We jointly examine the collected studies through four fundamental research questions (RQ1-4) that steer NT-FM development—identifying the prevailing model architectures, the network-data representations strategies, the networking tasks and environments addressed, and the available datasets.
- **Critical appraisal and research agenda.** We identify persistent gaps and distil them into a set of actionable research directions aimed at guiding both academic inquiry and industrial adoption.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 reviews task-specific ML in networking and foundation modelling elsewhere. Section 3 outlines literature collection and analysis process. Section 4 reports ‘Content Review’ (Section 4.1) and ‘Bibliometric Analysis’ (Section 4.2). ‘Discussion’ (Section 5) synthesises findings (Section 5.1) and future trends (Section 5.2). ‘Conclusion’ (Section 6) summarises our review of NT-FMs and key research implications.

2 Background & Related Work

2.1 Background

2.1.1 Network Traffic Analysis

The term “network traffic” refers to a temporally ordered stream of protocol data units exchanged between communicating endpoints. Its analysis is essential in modern network management, as infrastructures from home networks to hyperscale data centres operate at scales that prevent manual oversight from being viable [21–23].

Network management tasks include: (i) *Performance optimisation and resource management*, covering congestion control, dynamic bitrate adaptation, load balancing, routing, scheduling, orchestration, and QoS enforcement; (ii) *Predictive analytics*, such as Round-Trip Time (RTT) estimation, congestion forecasting, traffic-demand prediction, and PCAP failure detection; (iii) *Capacity planning*, through traffic generation, and predictive modelling for topology design; (iv) *Classification and identification*, enabling traffic shaping, protocol inference, and usage accounting; and (v) *Security and anomaly detection*, supporting intrusion or malware detection, Command & Control (C2) tracing, Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) localisation, Operating System (OS) fingerprinting, and fault diagnosis.

While monitoring network traffic is essential for performance, reliability and security, characterizing this traffic presents significant challenges because traffic spans diverse applications, protocol layers, encryption levels, and dynamic topologies. Thus, automated analysis pipelines integrate multi-granular sources; such as packet captures, flow summaries, control/application logs, and physical-layer telemetry; to capture semantic, volumetric, and contextual data [24].

Traffic characteristics vary by context: residential networks feature bursty multimedia flows; Industrial Control Systems (ICS) require low-latency, periodic exchanges; mobile networks add mobility-induced variability; and cloud infrastructures support both bulk replication and microservice traffic. Analytical methods must remain robust across these diverse scenarios [25].

Network traffic analysis progressed from rule-based systems, relying on handcrafted signatures but lacking adaptability; then to statistical and ML approaches, leveraging domain-specific features but vulnerable to drift; and now to DL models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), and Transformers, that learn directly from raw data and discover latent patterns [26].

Despite advances, ultra-high throughput requires sampling, sketching, and/or in-network processing to reduce loss and latency. Concurrently, encryption and heterogeneous domains demand privacy-preserving representations and transfer learning for generalisation. Additionally, sub-

millisecond inference and interpretability are key to real-world deployment.

Nevertheless, most traffic models are tightly coupled to specific datasets and tasks. Training is costly, and these models often fail in new environments or tasks, limiting reusability. Adopting foundation-model principles may enable generalisable, efficient models that adapt across network domains and operational objectives.

2.1.2 Foundation Models

Foundation models constitute a class of large-scale ML systems trained on extensive volumes of unlabelled data using self-supervised objectives, with the aim of acquiring generalisable representations that can be adapted to a broad spectrum of downstream tasks [9]. First introduced in the domain of NLP, they demonstrated that models could be pretrained on language corpora and subsequently fine-tuned to achieve state-of-the-art results across a range of linguistic problems. These tasks include text classification, translation, question answering, and summarisation [27, 28].

The general paradigm of foundation models is typically structured into two distinct phases:

- *Pretraining*: Exposing the model to vast quantities of unlabelled data while solving self-supervised tasks that encourage the acquisition of broadly applicable internal representations. These tasks may include masked token or next-sequence prediction, span corruption, contrastive learning, or generative modelling [9].
- *Fine-tuning*: Adapting the pretrained model to specific downstream applications by training it on smaller, labelled datasets. Fine-tuning can range from minimal adaptation in few-shot scenarios to extensive retraining depending on the task complexity and data availability.

The development of foundation models is closely tied to advances in model architectures and training strategies for self-supervised learning. Architectures such as Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [27] employ masked-language modelling, wherein parts of the input are obscured and the model is trained to reconstruct them, thereby learning contextual relationships within sequences. Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) models [28] expand upon this framework with autoregressive decoding, allowing them to generate coherent and contextually appropriate text continuations. These innovations made it possible for models to learn powerful representations of syntax and semantics without reliance on human-annotated labels.

Beyond NLP, foundation models have been successfully adopted in a variety of other domains, including computer vision, audio processing, robotics, and multimodal learning. In computer vision, models such as Vision Transformers (ViT) [29] and Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining (CLIP) [30] demonstrate that large-scale pretraining on image corpora yields representations that generalize well to

image classification, retrieval, and captioning tasks. In the speech domain, models like wav2vec [31] leverage raw audio data for unsupervised representation learning, improving performance in speech recognition and speaker identification. Robotics research increasingly explores foundation models to support general-purpose perception and planning [32], while multimodal models such as DALL-E [33] and Flamingo [34] integrate vision, text, and other sensory modalities to enable more comprehensive understanding and generation capabilities.

Despite their impressive capabilities, foundation models also raise several challenges. They demand substantial computational resources and training data, which may restrict their development and use to well-funded institutions [35]. Additionally, the opaqueness of their internal mechanisms poses concerns for interpretability and accountability, particularly in high-stakes applications. Questions about fairness, robustness, and the ethical implications of large-scale model training and deployment remain active areas of discussion [9, 36]. Furthermore, their strong reliance on pretraining data distribution can introduce hidden biases and limit generalisation when transferred to out-of-distribution settings [9].

By leveraging foundation models for network traffic management, we can treat traffic flows as a “language” whose patterns, anomalies, and dependencies are learned directly from raw data, eliminating the need for handcrafted features and protocol-specific heuristics. This approach promises more robust anomaly detection, adaptive QoS optimization, and dynamic resource allocation, as the model’s pretrained representations capture both short-term bursts and long-range traffic correlations. Moreover, fine-tuning on task-specific labelled traces enables rapid deployment across diverse network environments with minimal additional data.

Throughout the remainder of this paper, we perform a systematic literature review of foundation models applied to network traffic to identify current strengths, gaps, and future research directions.

2.2 Related Work

Recent work surveys the role of large-scale generative models throughout the networking domain. Bovenzi et al. [37] map the application of Generative AI—including GPT-style language models and diffusion models—to network monitoring and management tasks such as traffic generation, classification, and digital assistance. Complementing this panoramic view, Liu et al. [15] introduce a conceptual workflow for “LLM-for-Networking” that spans task definition through validation, while Zhou et al. [38] examine how language models can automate configuration, optimisation, and prediction in telecommunications infrastructures. These studies illuminate the breadth of use-cases but remain deliberately high-level. They offer little insight into how traffic is represented or what architectural patterns are emerging in foundation models trained directly

on packet or flow data. These are gaps that motivate the narrower focus of our review.

A second group of works investigates LLMs specifically for cyber-security. Hasanov et al. [39] and Hassanin & Moustafa [40] each conduct systematic surveys that catalogue how LLMs support threat intelligence, vulnerability assessment, intrusion detection, and incident response, while also discussing ethical and regulatory challenges. Their analyses, however, treat network traffic as just one data modality among many (logs, binaries, natural-language reports) and therefore stop short of dissecting the self-supervised pretraining objectives or tokenisation schemes required for traffic-centric models. Narrower empirical studies such as Bui et al. [41] and Kheddar [42] evaluate Transformer-based intrusion-detection pipelines, demonstrating that fine-tuned task-specific LLMs outperform prompt-based approaches, yet struggle with zero-day attacks. These works confirm the promise of foundation models for security tasks but focus on detection accuracy rather than on the foundation question of how to build and pretrain traffic models that generalise beyond a single application.

Encrypted-traffic analysis has emerged as the one networking niche where pretraining has been scrutinised in detail. Dong et al. [43] review DL and self-supervised techniques for classifying encrypted flows, highlighting graph representations, concept drift, and open-set conditions. Although methodologically close to our interests, their scope is confined to the encryption problem, leaving open how the same principles extend to mixed or unencrypted traffic contexts, and to tasks beyond classification.

Finally, Zhou et al. [44] survey pretrained foundation models across text, vision, and graphs, charting advances in scalability, security, and cross-domain transfer. Their cross-modal perspective underscores trends that influence networking research, yet the discussion is necessarily generic and does not interrogate the peculiar structure and temporal dynamics of network traffic.

Taken together, the existing literature establishes the relevance of generative and language model techniques for networking and security. However, it does so either from a broad applications angle or through the lens of a single downstream task. Our work differentiates itself by concentrating exclusively on foundation models whose training data comprise network traffic itself, systematically comparing their architectures, pretraining objectives, traffic representations, and deployment evidence across multiple networking environments, tasks, and datasets.

3 Methodology

Systematic literature reviews are rigorous, exhaustive, transparent, and replicable investigations that aggregate existing evidence through carefully designed, bias-minimised procedures applied across the leading scholarly databases [45].

To elaborate this study on NT-FMs, we have followed well established guidelines for performing a systematic literature review [46]. These directions were adapted to the characteristics of the topic and the fields of AI and networks, following previous published works in the field [41, 44, 47].

In the remainder of this section we outline the methodology adopted for the present study. First, we formulate the research questions and describe the search strategy (Sections 3.1 & 3.2). Next, we describe the selection criteria that determined which studies progressed to quantitative synthesis (Section 3.3). Finally, we report the number of records retained at each stage of the review workflow (Section 3.4).

3.1 Research Questions

The main objective of this study is to review the literature on the technical aspects of NT-FM development. Therefore, the Main Question (MQ) of our study is: *Is it feasible to develop NT-FMs?*. In particular, we aim to focus on AI architecture, type of training used, how network traffic is represented and encoded, how these models are applied to different network tasks, and which data sets were used to train these models. More formally, we formulate a set of Research Questions (RQs) in Table 1, that will guide our study.

Table 1: Formulated Research Questions (RQs) for the systematic literature review

ID	Research Question
MQ	<i>Is it feasible to develop NT-FMs?</i>
RQ1	Which AI architectures have been employed and how were they trained to develop NT-FMs?
RQ2	How is network traffic represented and encoded for input to NT-FMs?
RQ3	In which network environments and for which tasks have NT-FMs been applied?
RQ4	Are there publicly available datasets suitable for training NT-FMs?

3.2 Search Strategy

We retrieved the literature from *Web of Science Core Collection* (WoS) and *Scopus*, selected for their (i) broad coverage of core computer science and engineering venues, (ii) explicit source-selection policies, and (iii) structured citation metadata suitable for bibliometric analysis. Although other portals—such as *IEEE Xplore*, the *ACM Digital Library* and *ScienceDirect*—were considered, their content is largely indexed by *WoS* or *Scopus*, while their search interfaces do not support the complex Boolean equations required for our topic. *arXiv* preprints were also taken into account through *Scopus* preprint indexing service. The definitive list of controlled vocabulary and free-text keywords is shown in Table 4.

Given the novelty of NT-FMs, we adopted an inclusive stance towards publication types: peer-reviewed journal and conference papers, monographs, theses, and preprints were all eligible. The temporal window spans from 2017—the year in which the Transformer architecture was introduced [10], and therefore the start of the foundation models era—to 2025, thereby covering almost nine years of research activity.

Searches ran on 1 October 2024. The exact Boolean formulations used in each database are reproduced verbatim in Tables 2 and 3. Both queries restrict to English works published or posted as preprints from 2017/2025 (inclusive). We focus on peer-reviewed journals and conferences, but also include preprints and early-stage publications, given the topics novelty, to avoid missing relevant contributions not yet peer reviewed. We also consider grey literature, books, theses, standards, and patents. Additionally, we applied snowballing (reference inspection) to all selected articles, identifying further relevant works. Selection counts are detailed in Section 3.4.

Table 2: *Web of Science* search equation (executed 1 Oct. 2024).

```
TS=((("large language model*" OR "foundation*
model*" OR "general*" OR ((finetun* OR
"fine-tun*") AND (pretrain* OR "pretrain*")))
AND ("computer network*" OR "network traffic"
OR "network flow" OR "network packet*" OR
"network management" OR "network security" OR
"network administr*" OR "traffic administr*"
OR "raw packet*" OR "network trace*" OR
"packet* capture*" OR "traffic packet*" OR
"network message*" OR "data-driven network*"
OR "trace-driven network*" OR "network
protocol*" OR "packet* inspection" OR netflow
OR pcap* OR ipfix OR sflow OR "newly-generated
network flow*" OR nongf))
```

Table 3: *Scopus* search equation (executed 1 Oct. 2024).

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY(("large language model*" OR
"foundation* model*" OR "general*" OR
((finetun* OR "fine-tun*") AND (pretrain* OR
"pretrain*"))) AND ("computer network*" OR
"network traffic" OR "network flow" OR
"network packet*" OR "network management" OR
"network security" OR "network administr*" OR
"traffic administr*" OR "raw packet*" OR
"network trace*" OR "packet* capture*" OR
"traffic packet*" OR "network message*" OR
"data-driven network*" OR "trace-driven
network*" OR "network protocol*" OR "packet*
inspection" OR netflow OR pcap* OR ipfix OR
sflow OR "newly-generated network flow*" OR
nongf)) AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND PUBYEAR < 2026
AND (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "English"))
```

Table 4: Terms used in search equations, grouped by category

	AND	
	Foundation models	Network traffic
OR	"large language model*"; "foundation* model*"; "general*"; "finetun*"; "fine-tun*"; "pretrain*"; "pretrain*"	"computer network*"; "network traffic"; "network flow"; "network packet*"; "network management"; "network security"; "network administr*"; "traffic administr*"; "raw packet*"; "network trace*"; "packet* capture*"; "traffic packet*"; "network message*"; "data-driven network*"; "trace-driven network*"; "network protocol*"; "packet* inspection"; "netflow"; "pcap*"; "ipfix"; "sflow"; "newly-generated network flow*"; "nongf"

3.3 Study Selection Criteria

After the bibliographic searches had been executed and the exported records deduplicated, the screening phase was conducted with the *ASReview* platform [48]. *ASReview* is an open-source, active-learning tool that iteratively prioritises references for inspection by learning from the reviewer’s previous inclusion-exclusion decisions. Compared with conventional spreadsheet checking, the approach markedly reduces screening effort while preserving high recall; every action is logged, facilitating full auditability and reproducibility of the decision trail. The interface presents each candidate study with its title, list of author-supplied keywords and abstract, thereby allowing a rapid relevance judgement without opening the full text.

In the present review, an initial seed set comprising five undoubtedly relevant NT-FM papers was provided to train the underlying classifier. Titles, keywords, and abstracts were inspected in the order suggested by the algorithm. When the title-abstract triage left the relevance of a reference ambiguous, the full text was retrieved and read in depth before a final screening decision was made. For instance, when the abstract hinted at network traffic but did not specify the training paradigm. Table 5 contains the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to each reference.

Applying these rules ensured that the final corpus remained closely aligned with the review’s research questions. The studies admitted after this filtering step were subsequently examined in depth to address each research question detailed in Section 3.1.

3.4 Corpus Collected & Reviewed

The search protocol retrieved 5373 records in total, where 973 were from the *Web of Science Core Collection* and 4400 from *Scopus*. Deduplication based on titles, DOIs, and author lists eliminated 1405 items, yielding 3968 unique references for screening. These were loaded into *ASReview*, whose active-learning algorithm presented the most promising studies first; 835 records survived this machine-assisted triage, whereas 3133 were discarded as clearly irrelevant. The remaining set was assessed against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, reducing the pool to 92 candidate papers. A full-text examination of those 92 studies left 39 that fully satisfied every eligibility requirement and were therefore entered into the quantitative synthesis.

The corpus was subsequently updated through two complementary techniques. Automated alerting on *WoS* and *Scopus* identified 6 recently published works that were added to the review. Similarly, backward-forward snowballing through reference lists and citation graphs contributed another 6. Consequently, the final body of literature comprises 51 articles. Figure 3.4 illustrates the PRISMA diagram with the entire identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion workflow, together with the numbers of records retained and excluded at each stage.

Table 5: Inclusion (IC) and Exclusion (EC) criteria.

Type	Criterion
IC1	Foundation models applied to networking.
IC2	Demonstrated generalisation across data distributions, network environments, distinct tasks or different granularities of the same task.
IC3	Workflows that start with pretraining and later adapt the model through fine-, few- or zero-shot learning.
IC4	Training and evaluation based on computer-network data at any level: packets, flows, sessions, headers, payloads, application-layer traces, etc.
EC1	Approaches that do not include a pretraining stage.
EC2	Training based on non-network or physical-layer data (URLs, logs, textual reports, signals, RF traces, etc.).
EC3	Focus on non-computer-network domains such as road traffic or power-grid networks.
EC4	Publication is a short introductory paper, early access, or conference abstract.
EC5	Publication not in English.
EC6	Document is not available for download or reading.
EC7	Publication is duplicated.
EC8	Published outside the 2017 - 2025 time window.
EC9	Retracted publications.

Figure 2: PRISMA diagram of the systematic review protocol.

4 Results

This section presents the results of the systematic literature review. (Section 4.1) provides a content-based description of the analysed works, organised chronologically to highlight the progression of the field. In (Section 4.2), we conduct a bibliometric analysis of the collected corpus.

4.1 Content Review

This section chronologically reviews the analysed studies to show how the field has evolved. For this purpose, we classify the works into three categories. Section 4.1.1 includes those that introduce a pretraining & fine-tuning pipeline tailored to address a single network task or a specific environment, without aiming to achieve generalisation across diverse network scenarios. Section 4.1.2 contains works that propose a complete NT-FM, demonstrating generalisation capabilities across multiple network tasks and environments. In Section 4.1.3, we analyse some additional works that were found relevant enough to be

mentioned in this review, despite not being included in the corpus according to the inclusion/exclusion criteria.

4.1.1 Pretraining and fine-tuning in specific environments or tasks

Transformers, contrastive encoders, and masked-autoencoders have quickly become dominant of modern network traffic research. Yet, between 2020 and 2024, the vast majority of studies adopted these techniques to build task- or environment-specific models rather than genuinely foundation ones. Before 2020, there is no published work at this point. The present subsection traces this evolution chronologically, showing how each contribution incrementally broadened the range of architectures, data representations, and self-supervised objectives, while ultimately remaining confined to a single operational context.

2020: Compact transformers on byte streams

The first attempts to port language-model pretraining to packet data relied on lightweight Transformer backbones originally devised for textual corpora. Han et al. [49] replaced ALBERT’s 32 K-token vocabulary with 256 byte tokens, framing each packet as a “sentence” and each flow as a “document”. Using only masked-byte modelling for pretraining, the authors achieved inference times under 20ms while surpassing a full-sized BERT in binary malware classification on ISCX-2012/2017. Almost in parallel, He et al. [50] introduced PERT, a BERT-like encoder whose dynamic tokeniser yields context-aware embeddings for encrypted payloads. The model learned solely from unlabelled TLS traces and, once fine-tuned, generalised to proprietary monitoring data without manual feature engineering. Both studies demonstrated that bidirectional self-attention, even in heavily parameter-shared form, is well-suited to byte sequences. They established the canonical two-stage workflow—large unlabelled pretraining followed by task-specific fine-tuning—that would dominate the field thereafter. Nevertheless, each work focused on a single pair of public datasets and addressed exactly one downstream task: malware versus benign traffic ([49]) and service identification within encrypted channels ([50]), respectively.

2022: Broadening architectures and tackling open sets

By 2022 researchers began to graft convolutional and semi-supervised components onto the Transformer core so as to cope with unlabelled or previously unseen classes. OpenCBD [51] combined a CNN with a Transformer encoder inside a multi-stage “Closed-to-Be-Discovered” (CBD) pipeline. Self-supervised pretraining produced latent representations on ISCXVPN2016, after which a purpose-built H_2 -loss encouraged large margins between known and unknown classes. In a similar vein, MT-FlowFormer [52] abandoned raw bytes in favour of 84 statistical flow features and embedded them hierarchically. A mean-teacher scheme distilled knowledge from millions of unlabelled flows, lowering annotation needs to 10 %

whilst maintaining state-of-the-art VPN recognition. Importantly, both studies retained full control of the evaluation domain—VPN or anonymity network backbones—so the resulting encoders were never tested beyond those milieus.

Scarcity of annotated traffic next motivated few-shot and open-set frameworks grounded in contrastive learning. Li et al. [53] applied Barlow Twins to traffic tensors augmented through block replication and feature disruption. A ResNet-12 encoder, fine-tuned with a centroid classifier, achieved robust TLS service recognition from as few as five examples. Meanwhile NorBERT [54] introduced a domain-aware tokeniser for Fully-Qualified Domain Names (FQDNs). Its masked language modelling objective fostered embeddings that cluster unseen IoT devices by manufacturer, thereby illustrating how linguistic inductive biases can handle hierarchical network identifiers. Both papers represent creative answers to the tokenisation and label-efficiency challenges, yet each considered only a single class of input objects—payload or FQDN strings—inside a unique environment.

2023: Vision-language hybrids, synthetic data and domain-tailored contrastive learning

In 2023, we saw a burst of multimodal architectures that reinterpret traffic flows as images or generate synthetic samples to counter privacy barriers. MLST-FENet [55] mapped packet sequences onto greyscale matrices, extracted spatial features via CNNs, captured temporal dependencies through Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory networks (BiLSTMs), and applied coordinate attention to enhance salience. Tested on USTC-TFC2016 and ISCX VPN-nonVPN, the model gained precision, underscoring how vision techniques can rival purely token-based approaches.

Whereas MLST-FENet strives for better classifiers, PAC-GPT [56] tackles the inverse problem: data generation. A GPT-3 flow generator coordinates packet sequences that a second GPT-3 module realises byte-by-byte, thereby producing privacy-preserving traffic replicas for IDS experimentation. The synthetic flows preserved protocol-level statistics and replayed successfully in network emulators. However, the study did not examine cross-task transfer as the GPTs were trained and evaluated solely for traffic mimicking.

In the IoT realm, self-supervised MoCo-v2 contrastive learning proved fruitful for flow-image encoders. Almaraz-Rivera et al. [57] pretrained on Bot-IoT and LATAM-DDoS-IoT before fine-tuning a lightweight classifier that surpassed fully supervised baselines in detecting DDoS bursts. Again, the improvement was confined to a single threat class and environment; no evidence was provided for transfer beyond DDoS or IoT.

2024: Rich self-supervised objectives and the rise of large language models

By 2024, the literature had diversified both objective functions and evaluation domains. EM-BERT [58] reconstructed TLS sessions, tokenised hexadecimal words, and fine-tuned a binary classifier that reached >99.9 % precision across USTC-TFC2016, Malware-Traffic-Analysis, and a proprietary EVERSEC set. Despite involving three datasets, the study still addressed one task—malware versus benign flows—and did not report multi-task generalisation.

Intrusion prediction rather than detection emerged in the GPT-BERT-LSTM pipeline of Diaf et al. [59]. A causal GPT forecasts the next packet in a flow; BERT validates the prediction’s plausibility; an LSTM then flags malicious sequences. On CICIoT2023 the three-stage system achieved 98 % binary accuracy, but the architecture was purpose-built for IoT packet streams and did not transfer outside this domain.

To automate architecture design under few-shot constraints, the NAS-based FS-MTC framework [60] searched CNN-LSTM candidates using auxiliary malware corpora. The resulting topology attained 86.9 % one-shot accuracy yet remained restricted to malware classification. Similarly, the IoT-oriented TabTransformer variant ITCT [61] masked categorical MQTT fields and reached 82 % accuracy in a lightweight model suitable for resource-constrained sensors, but again targeted a single protocol.

Masked-autoencoders (MAEs) entered the scene through MTC-MAE [62]. By randomly masking 75 % of pixels in 28×28 flow images, the model learned universal malware features that delivered 98.4 % accuracy with only 5 % labels. Yet, despite proving robustness to encrypted and IoT variants, MTC-MAE still centred on malware detection exclusively. Comparable specialisation characterises IoV-BERT-IDS [63], whose semantic extractor converts in-car and out-of-car frames into “byte sentences” processed by BERT. Extensive cross-vehicle experiments confirm generalisation across vehicle models, but the scope remains vehicular intrusion detection.

Handling long sequences in encrypted channels motivated LAMBERT [64]. A stacked Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (BiGRU) on top of BERT captured temporal dependencies missed by pure self-attention, yielding >99 % F1 on imbalanced TLS corpora. SSCL-IDS [65] adopted benign-only contrastive pretraining with corruption masks, boosting AUROC by up to 27 % versus supervised baselines over five IDS datasets. Both studies refined objective design but stayed within the IDS problem space.

LLMs properly entered network security via Quantized Low-Rank Adapter (QLoRA) fine-tuning of Llama2 for DDoS flow textification [66]. The method converted numerical feature vectors into structured sentences that an LLM classified with 99.2 % accuracy, outperforming CNNs/LSTMs while running under 4-bit quantisation. DistilBERT underpins LLMcap [67], which tokenises PCAP

dictionaries and learns to predict failure events with a 20 % masking rate. Despite high F1 in VoLTE/VoNR traces, the model struggled to generalise to structurally dissimilar NSA connectivity logs.

Graph and state-space paradigms further diversified the landscape. Few-shot graph contrastive learning [68] built temporal attributed multi-graphs for SCADA traffic, achieving superior F1 in one-shot ICS attack recognition. Chu et al. [69] demonstrated that selective state-space models (Mamba) surpass Transformer diffusers in synthesising realistic PCAP traces for video and social media workloads. Still, both studies served single verticals—ICS defence and traffic generation—without cross-domain evaluation.

Vehicular research progressed via Auto-CIDS [70], a multi-agent deep-reinforcement IDS that self-supervises on Controller Area Network (CAN) frames through autoencoders, clustering and isolation forests. Public Car-Hacking data validated high recall for DoS and spoofing attacks, yet the agents were trained exclusively on automotive messages. Finally, AppCL-Header-BERT [71] showed that header-only tokens—omitting IPs and ports—suffice for 99 % F1 service classification on ISCX VPN-nonVPN, raising privacy while retaining accuracy. Although, the model was only evaluated on a single service-label dataset.

4.1.2 Network Traffic Foundation Models

Foundation models have revolutionised NLP and CV by exploiting vast unlabelled corpora and self-supervised objectives to learn general representations that can be transferred to a multitude of downstream tasks. Motivated by these advances, networking researchers have begun to ask whether analogous NT-FMs can be trained once on heterogeneous packet traces and subsequently fine-tuned—often with only a handful of labelled samples—for classification, forecasting, generation, and interactive analytics. In the paragraphs that follow we chart the chronological development of NT-FMs from 2022 to early 2025, weaving together 25 primary studies and highlighting the architectural, representational, and evaluative innovations that have shaped this fast-moving field.

2022: The inaugural Transformer era

To the best of our knowledge, the first proposal of a complete NT-FM was ET-BERT [7], directly porting BERT’s bidirectional self-attention to encrypted traffic classification. Recognising that encrypted flows lack the textual semantics on which BERT was originally trained, the authors crafted two bespoke self-supervised tasks. The Masked BURST Model randomly masks contiguous byte bursts within TLS records, compelling the model to infer low-level lexical and syntactic regularities. The Same-origin BURST Prediction task forces ET-BERT to reason over flow-level structure by deciding whether two datagrams originate from the same session. A Datagram2Token pipeline segments packets into language-like tokens, preserving header-payload boundaries without revealing plaintext. Fine-tuned on five public and proprietary datasets,

ET-BERT set new state-of-the-art results on VPN, Tor, and TLS 1.3 traffic, establishing the feasibility of Transformer backbones for encrypted networking workloads.

In parallel, Ray’s thesis introduced the Network Traffic Transformer (NTT) [72], subsequently published as a conference paper in Dietmüller et al. [6]. Whereas ET-BERT targeted application recognition, NTT tackled temporal performance prediction. Packet sequences were hierarchically aggregated into multi-timescale windows, allowing the model to maintain packet-level granularity within a manageable attention footprint. Self-supervised pretraining masked inter-packet delays—akin to masked language modelling but on timing residuals—aligning the latent space with queuing dynamics and congestion signals. After a single pretraining run on synthetic ns-3 traffic, the same weights could be fine-tuned for delay estimation and message completion-time prediction across a variety of new topologies with far less data than required by recurrent or ARIMA baselines. These results demonstrated, for the first time, that a single model could migrate between performance-oriented tasks and network configurations.

Complementing these empirical efforts, Le et al. published a theoretical visionary position paper on “Re-thinking Data-driven Networking with Foundation Models” [8]. The authors argued that network traces, like text, are richly hierarchical. They are imbued with protocol syntax, temporal rhythms, and semantic usage patterns. They identified three open problems: (i) defining cross-protocol tokenisation schemes that span Ethernet, IP, TLS, and emerging protocols; (ii) engineering pretraining objectives that respect the multi-party, multi-layer nature of communication; and (iii) curating public benchmarks to ensure rigorous, reproducible evaluation. Their agenda has since served as a lodestar for subsequent NT-FM research.

2023: From discriminative to generative paradigms

In 2023, a notable transition from solely discriminative objectives to models capable of generation occurred. NetGPT [73] adapted GPT-2 to hex-token sequences, embedding header boundaries via reserved control tokens and randomly shuffling non-functional header fields during pretraining. These augmentations encouraged the model to disentangle syntactic invariants from semantic payload heterogeneity. Evaluations showed that NetGPT not only excelled at conventional classification tasks, such as malware and industrial-protocol detection, but also synthesised realistic flows that fooled deep ensemble classifiers. This dual classification-generation capability signalled that autoregressive objectives can yield representations sufficiently flexible for both inference and traffic synthesis, thereby broadening the scope of NT-FM applications.

Concurrent to NetGPT, Zhao et al. proposed YaTC [74, 75], introducing a Multi-level Flow Representation (MFR) matrix that encodes byte, packet, and flow statistics in a single two-dimensional structure. A MAE reconstructs randomly masked rows and columns, forcing the model to capture correlations across granularities. Fine-tuning

on five encryption-heavy datasets, YaTC surpassed ET-BERT by up to six percentage points on F1 while requiring markedly fewer labels. Building upon similar principles, netFound [18] injected an additional modality—statistical flow metadata—into a hierarchical Transformer, leveraging skip connections to process extensive sequences and demonstrating resilience to noisy or missing labels. Together, these 2023 studies consolidated Transformers as the de-facto NT-FM backbone, while introducing multimodality and generation as first-class citizens.

2024: Proliferation and diversification

A growing recognition that real-world deployments require both understanding and synthesis led to hybrid encoder-decoder frameworks. Lens [76] repurposed T5, melding masked-span, packet-order, and homologous-flow prediction into a single pretraining cocktail. A privacy-preserving hex tokeniser built on WordPiece enabled Lens to encode VPN, IoT, and mobile flows alike. The model delivered a 10.75 % average accuracy uplift over strong baselines on six datasets and simultaneously generated flows with 62 % lower divergence from empirical distributions. TrafficGPT [77] tackled the notorious 512-token limit of vanilla GPT by introducing linear attention and a reversible token map, scaling to 12 032 tokens per flow. This innovation unlocked faithful modelling of long-running sessions such as adaptive bitrate streaming and bulk uploads, outperforming GAN-based generators on Jensen-Shannon divergence and packet-header realism. In a related but coarser domain, NetFlowGen [78] applied a decoder-only Transformer to minute-aggregated NetFlow statistics, fine-tuning a lightweight classifier for early DDoS warning without surrendering privacy by inspecting payloads.

While generative capacity blossomed, deployment pragmatics drove research into parameter-efficient adaptation. EAT [79] froze all pretrained TPTM parameters, inserting 3.4 %-sized bottleneck adapters between Transformer layers and achieving 98.54 % accuracy on ISCX-VPN with a 96.6 % parameter reduction relative to full fine-tuning. PETReLM [80] added LoRA rank-update matrices to BERT, cutting fine-tuned parameters by over 90 % while matching ET-BERT across VPN, Tor, and IoT benchmarks.

Tokenisation and representation continued to evolve. FlowPiece-ALBERT [81] embedded contextual information directly within tokens, constructing identifier prefixes that disambiguate payload segments, a strategy that preserved performance despite a 93 % parameter reduction afforded by ALBERT’s factorised embedding layers. CETP [82] addressed class imbalance via a dual objective combining contrastive instance discrimination with masked token reconstruction, supplemented by pseudo-labelling and dynamic loss weighting during fine-tuning. CETP achieved a 10.19 % F1 improvement on ISCX-VPN without manual rebalance. In parallel, the GETRF [83] embraced datagram-aware byte-pair encoding and introduced Same Packet Prediction and Hidden State Feature Prediction, realising 99.12 % F1 across five tasks and pub-

lishing the first public encrypted-traffic corpus suitable for Transformer pretraining.

Architectural diversity also widened. NetMamba [20] replaced quadratic self-attention with a linear-time state-space model, incorporating stride-based windows that retain hierarchical flow context while achieving up to $60\times$ faster inference and minimal memory usage. GNN-FM [19] departed entirely from sequence models, representing flows and addresses as nodes in spatio-temporal graphs. They have yielded embeddings that, when fine-tuned, improved intrusion-detection F1 by 6.87 % while shrinking parameters by two orders of magnitude.

Beyond backbone variations, researchers explored multimodal contrastive learning. CoMDet [84] jointly encoded TLS handshake bytes, packet-length sequences, and inter-arrival intervals, aligning representations via a contrastive loss that maximises inter-modal mutual information. Following this approach, they detected malicious encrypted flows at 92 % accuracy with only 80 labels per class. MI-ETT [85] introduced two-level attention for intra- and inter-packet relations, surpassing ET-BERT and YaTC on five datasets without sacrificing efficiency.

With a burgeoning menagerie of architectures, the community recognised the need for rigorous comparison. Net-Bench [86] amalgamated seven public datasets into fifteen classification and five generation tasks, prescribing uniform preprocessing to eliminate confounding variables. Benchmark results confirmed that YaTC [75] and ET-BERT [7] still lead discriminative accuracy, while generative NT-FMs such as NetGPT [73] and TrafficGPT [77] excel at synthesis realism, thereby delivering the first comprehensive yardstick for NT-FM progress.

2025: Efficiency and robustness

The current wave of research focuses on efficiency and robustness. EAPT [87] integrates disentangled attention, SentencePiece tokenisation, and an adversarial Replaced Burst Detection objective. This strategy yields YaTC accuracy while using only 20 % of its parameters and 13 % of its pre-training corpus—an attractive proposition for privacy-conscious operators. MLETC [88] extends DeBERTa with separate TCP and UDP encoders, and field-aware masking, achieving 98-99 % F1 across Tor, VPN, and campus traffic. These contributions suggest that the NT-FM research cycle is converging toward lightweight yet durable architectures capable of thriving under adversarial conditions and data scarcity.

Taken together, the 2022-2025 literature paints a vivid picture of rapid, multi-faceted innovation. Before 2022, no published work were found that proposed a complete NT-FM. Starting from BERT-style byte masking, the field has embraced state-space and graph neural backbones, temporal aggregation, multimodal contrastive learning, autoregressive generation, parameter-efficient adaptation and standardised benchmarks. Each step has broadened the functional envelope of NT-FMs, inching the community

closer to the long-term goal of training once, deploying everywhere.

4.1.3 Other Relevant Works

Several pertinent studies were located during the review, but they were excluded from the core corpus because they do not provide genuine NT-FMs. Most reuse LLMs pre-trained on natural language and target network management or single-task analytics rather than general traffic understanding, thereby violating criteria IC2 and EC1-3. However, we found these works enough relevant into the field to be cited in this work, even though they are not further analysed nor counted as part of the corpus.

LLM-centric network-management works include NetGPT [89], which merges cloud- and edge-hosted LLMs for intent inference and popularity prediction; Donadel et al. [90], which assess LLM comprehension of topologies for virtual system-administration; ShieldGPT [91], an LLM reasoning engine for DDoS defence; NET-BERT [92], a text-oriented networking LLM; and NetLLM [93], whose customised “Networking Head” produces task-specific outputs (e.g., viewport or bitrate predictions), distancing it from a traffic foundation model. These studies ignore raw traffic (EC2/3) or lack cross-task generality (IC2).

A second group repurposes text LLMs for single traffic tasks by converting packets to “sentences”. Cui et al. [94], De la Torre et al. [95], Ginige et al. [96], Guastalla et al. [97], Hassanin et al. [98], Lai [99], Adjewa et al. [100] and Hu et al. [101] respectively address generic traffic embedding, trace comprehension, encrypted classification, DDoS detection, cyber-threat and intrusion detection (including federated 5G), and wireless prediction. Despite innovation, they employ non-native pretraining and remain task-bound, breaching IC2 and/or EC1.

Finally, several works fall outside computer-network traffic or are auxiliary tools: García et al. [102] (time-series anomaly FM); Ott et al. [103] (5G localisation FM); Jiang et al. [104] (traffic augmentation via diffusion); Luxemburk et al. [105] (dataset-management toolbox); and Zong et al. [106] (attention-based encrypted classification without FM pretraining, violating EC1/IC3). Consequently, none qualify as NT-FMs.

4.2 Bibliometric Analysis

The systematic search retrieved a total of 51 primary studies, whose descriptive statistics reveal a research stream that is nascent yet already showing signs of consolidation. The overall publication mix (Figure 3b) aligns with computer science dissemination norms; nearly half the items are conference papers, a third are journal articles and a fifth circulate as pre-prints, while just one thesis underscores the field’s nascent character. This distribution signals a community valuing the rapid visibility of conference deadlines and *arXiv* e-prints, yet increasingly

pursuing the permanence and citation weight of archival journals.

Temporal output (Figure 3a) confirms a marked inflection. After two isolated contributions in 2020 and a dormant 2021, the annual count rose to eight in both 2022 and 2023 before quadrupling to 31 in 2024. All document types contributed to that surge, though journals (1 to 10 papers) and conference proceedings (6 to 15) saw the sharpest increases. The trend suggests continued growth in 2025, even though only two early-access articles are currently indexed; the lag is explained by analysis and publication lead times.

The venue landscape remains highly fragmented (Figure 4). 9 of the 51 studies appear solely on *arXiv*, underlining the tendency toward for immediate dissemination. Only *IEEE Access*, *Computer Networks*, *Sensors*, and the *HotNets* workshop host more than one contribution apiece, while a long tail of 33 additional venues records singletons ranging from flagship AI fora (*AAAI*, *KDD*) to specialised workshops (e.g. *TMA*, *OTCON*). For practitioners this dispersion complicates horizon scanning; no “canonical” outlet has yet emerged, and staying current demands monitoring an unusually broad publication spectrum.

When the studies are categorised by objective—either delivering an end-to-end NT-FM or just supplying a pretraining & fine-tuning pipeline for a specific network task/environment (PreFin)—the split is nearly exact (Figure 5). Twenty-six papers (51 %) focus on reusable pretraining pipelines, while the remaining twenty-five (49 %) present self-contained foundation models such as ET-BERT [7], netFound [18] or NetGPT [73]. This parity is significant: unlike vision and language, where foundation model primacy is largely settled, network traffic research still regards bespoke pretraining as a viable path.

A VOSviewer overlay of bibliographic coupling (Figure 6) shows intellectual influence already coalescing around a compact set of highly-linked documents. Papers by Lin, He and Zhao define an intense “blue core” centred on 2022 contributions such as ET-BERT; more recent works appear towards the red spectrum, yet many share references with that initial core, indicating a cumulative-rather than disruptive-expansion of knowledge. This pattern is amplified in the direct-citation network (Figure 7), whose core-periphery geometry shows the same cluster of early studies acting as obligatory waypoints for later authors, signalling that the field is converging on foundation methodological baselines.

The conceptual structure extracted from titles and abstracts (Figure 8) corroborates the multi-disciplinarity suggested by the document networks. Five topical clusters are evident. The green component groups classic networking terms (“computer security”, “quality of service”); the yellow cluster collocates modelling primitives (“transformer”, “deep learning”); red nodes capture packet-level artefacts (“network packet”, “intrusion detection system”);

Figure 3: Summary of the $n = 51$ studies included in our corpus and analysed in the systematic review on NT-FMs. (a) Year-by-year publication counts (2020 - 2025) broken down by dissemination venue-journal articles, conference papers, pre-prints and theses. The grey spline represents the trend line, emphasising the accelerating growth of the field. (b) Overall distribution of publication types: conference papers represent almost half of the corpus (24; 47%), followed by journal articles (16; 31%), pre-prints (10; 20%) and a single thesis (1; 2%).

Figure 4: Number of publications per venue for the sources. Bars are colour-coded by publication type. *arXiv* leads with nine preprints; *IEEE Access*, *Computer Networks* and *Sensors* journals each show two publications, as well as *HotNets* conference; while all other listed venues contain a single publication.

Figure 5: Distribution of NT-FM versus PreFin publications. Donut chart summarising the 51 papers classified by: PreFin (light pink, 26 publications = 51%) and NT-FM (dark pink, 25 publications = 49%).

Figure 6: VOSviewer network visualization of bibliographic coupling with documents as the unit of analysis. Each node is an individual publication; edge thickness is proportional to the number of references the two documents share (coupling strength), while node size reflects a document’s total link strength. The blue-red colour gradient is the overlay visualisation, indicating publication year from 2022 (blue) to 2024 (red).

Figure 7: VOSviewer network visualisation of direct citation links between documents. Nodes correspond to publications and are scaled by total link strength (citations exchanged with other items); links represent undirected citation relations.

Figure 8: VOSviewer term-map of keyword co-occurrence with concepts extracted from document titles/abstracts. Node size shows term frequency; link thickness indicates the number of documents in which two terms co-occur. Colours denote clusters identified by VOSviewer’s modularity-based clustering algorithm, revealing thematic groupings within the corpus.

blue terms denote the methodological substrate (“mathematics”, “generalisation”); and a smaller purple set highlights protocol-specific topics. Dense inter-cluster links reflect the composite nature of modern solutions, which blend byte-level tokenisation with flow-level semantics and, increasingly, generative objective.

We also analysed the geographical distribution of publications. For this, we considered the countries of the authors’ affiliated institutions. Figure 9 exposes a markedly uneven global footprint across the 51 studies. Nearly half the corpus emanates from Asia, led by China’s 27 publications (43%), dwarfing all other national contributions. The United States follows with 9 papers (14%), while Japan adds 3. A small cluster of high-income nations—Canada, the United Kingdom, France, Switzerland and the Republic of Korea—produce 2 papers each, signifying localised activity within Europe and North America. The remaining 14 countries, scattered across 5 continents, furnish a single study apiece, underscoring the field’s nascent and geographically concentrated character. Europe, despite comprising 10 publishing nations, yields fewer than one-quarter of all papers, indicating fragmentation rather than critical mass. Representation from Latin America (Brazil, Colombia, Mexico) and Africa (Algeria) is embryonic, and Oceania is absent. These disparities invite broader interna-

tional collaboration to temper regional biases and stimulate future innovation.

Taken together, these bibliometric signals depict a domain expanding rapidly, publishing diffusely and beginning to consolidate around a small, central canon. The practical implications are threefold. First, systematic surveillance of pre-print servers remains essential, as many seminal papers surface there long before peer-reviewed publication. Additionally, partnerships with the central author cluster may accelerate replication and benchmarking, helping mitigate the scarcity of standardised datasets and evaluation pipelines. Moreover, several conceptual niches—state-space models for traffic synthesis, graph-based flow representations or cross-protocol multilingualism—remain lightly populated, suggesting fertile ground for high-impact contributions that can shape the next wave of foundation-model research in networking.

Figure 9: Global distribution of the 51 publications of our corpus. Colour intensity encodes the absolute number of papers per country (see colour-bar), with China (27) dominating, followed by the United States (9) and Japan (3); fourteen further nations appear as single-paper contributors, evidencing the field’s current geographical concentration.

5 Discussion

This section presents a discussion of the studies collected and examined in this systematic review. Section 5.1 provides a synthesis of the reviewed studies in relation to each of the Research Questions (RQs) initially posed in this work, with the objective of offering substantiated answers to each. Section 5.2 presents the future research directions emerging both from the reviewed literature and from insights derived through our own critical analysis.

It is worth mentioning that, given that the primary aim of the review was to address the Main Question (MQ) “Is it feasible to develop NT-FMs?”, only those works previously classified as “NT-FMs” were considered in this section. These works propose complete foundation models aimed at achieving generalisation across a range of networking tasks. We regard them as representative of this line of research, and therefore distinguish them from the remaining studies, which are more limited in their pursuit of generalisation across tasks and network environments.

5.1 Synthesis by Research Questions

5.1.1 RQ1: Which AI architectures have been employed and how were they trained to develop NT-FMs?

The development of NT-FMs has predominantly leveraged architectures successful in other domains, primarily the Transformer, adapted to the unique characteristics of network traffic data. The most relevant architecture

was Transformer-based models, including variants such as BERT, GPT, T5, DeBERTa, and ALBERT, forming the core of most proposed NT-FMs (Table 6). However, other architectures like Mamba, GNNs, and multi-modal CNNs combined with Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) have also been explored, although in a minor way. The prevailing training paradigm for these models is a two-stage process: (i) self-supervised pretraining on large volumes of unlabeled network data, followed by (ii) supervised fine-tuning on smaller, task-specific labelled datasets.

Architectural enhancements to the Transformer aim to capture the hierarchical and temporal nature of network traffic. Hierarchical attention mechanisms are common, exemplified by the MIETT with its Two-Level Attention [85], netFound’s Burst and Flow Encoders with skip connections [18], and the NTT with its hierarchical aggregation layer [6]. YaTC employs distinct Packet-Level and Flow-Level Attention modules [75]. Other innovations include disentangled attention mechanisms that separate content and relative position embeddings [87, 88], and the use of linear attention to handle significantly longer sequences more efficiently than traditional quadratic self-attention [77]. While some models adopt an encoder-decoder structure (e.g., T5 in [76]), others utilise a decoder-only, auto-regressive design akin to GPT-2 [73, 78]. Multi-modal inputs are also integrated, with CoMDet employing three independent Transformer encoders for different traffic modalities [84], and netFound using multi-modal embeddings that combine packet field, positional, and meta-data information [18]. Parameter sharing across layers or

Table 6: Comparison of NT-FMs (1): The table includes model architectures, parameter sizes, pretraining tasks, number of downstream tasks (#FN tasks), and availability of public code and model weights. Models are listed alphabetically with citations referencing their original works.

Model	Architecture	#Params	Pretraining task(s)	#FN tasks	Public code	Public models
ALBERT [81]	ALBERT - Transformer (Encoder)	9M	(1) Masked Flow Model	3	-	-
CETP [82]	Transformer (Encoder)	-	(1) Contrastive Learning Model (2) Masked Sequence Model	5	-	-
CoMDet [84]	Transformer (Encoder)	-	(1) Inter-modal contrastive learning	1	-	-
EAPT [87]	Transformer (Encoder)	22M	(1) Replaced BURST Detection	5	-	-
ET-BERT [7]	Transformer (Encoder)	110M	(1) Masked BURST Model (2) Same-origin BURST Prediction	7	✓	✓
GETRF [83]	Transformer (Encoder)	343M	(1) Mask Token Prediction (2) Same Packet Prediction (3) Hidden State Feature Prediction	5	-	-
GNN-FM [19]	GNN	732k	(1) Link Prediction	3	✓	-
Lens [76]	T5 - Transformer (Encoder-Decoder)	250M	(1) Masked Span Prediction (2) Packet Order Prediction (3) Homologous Traffic Prediction	20	-	-
MIETT [85]	Transformer (Encoder)	-	(1) Masked Flow Prediction (2) Packet Relative Position Prediction (3) Flow Contrastive Learning	5	✓	-
MLETC [88]	DeBERTa - Transformer (Encoder)	-	(1) Masked Fields Prediction (2) Same Origin Flow Prediction	4	-	-
NetFlowGen [78]	GPT - Transformer (Decoder)	1.9-25M	(1) Next-step Traffic Prediction	1	-	-
NetGPT [73]	GPT-2 - Transformer (Decoder)	100M	(1) Autoregressive Next Token Prediction	9	✓	✓
NetMamba [20]	Mamba - State Space Model	2.2M	(1) Masked Autoencoder	6	✓	✓
netFound [18]	Transformer (Encoder)	640M	(1) Masked Token Prediction	5	✓	✓
NTT [6, 72]	Transformer (Encoder)	-	(1) End-to-end Delay Prediction	2	✓	-
PETReLM [80]	BERT - Transformer (Encoder)	7.7M	(1) Masked Language Model (2) Modified Next Sentence Prediction	5	✓	-
TrafficGPT [77]	Transformer (Decoder)	-	(1) Autoregressive Pretraining	5	-	-
YaTC [74, 75]	Vision Transformer (Encoder-Decoder)	-	(1) Masked Autoencoder	6	✓	✓

between encoder components is a strategy used to reduce model size and improve stability [75, 80, 81].

Beyond Transformers, other architectures have been explored. NetMamba introduces the Mamba architecture, a linear-time State Space Model (SSM), as an efficient alternative to Transformers for sequential network traffic data, employing a unidirectional Mamba variant with a content-aware selection mechanism and stride cutting for input representation [20]. For graph-based NT-FMs, a spatio-temporal GNN built on the GraphSAGE framework is proposed, representing network flows and IP addresses as nodes with spatial and temporal edges [19].

The scale of these NT-FMs varies significantly (Table 6). Dedicated NT-FMs range from hundreds of millions of parameters (e.g., netFound with 640M [18], Lens with 250M [76], NetGPT with 100M [73], ET-BERT implicitly around 110M [7]) to more compact designs (e.g., EAPT with 22M [87], ALBERT-based model with 9M [81], PE-TRoLM with 7.7M [80] NetMamba with 2.2M [20], NetFlowGen with 1.9M [78], and the graph-based model with approximately 732k parameters [19]). It is worth mentioning that some of the works do not explicitly set the size or number of parameters of their models.

Various pretraining tasks have been employed to develop NT-FMs, primarily leveraging self-supervised learning on large, unlabeled datasets to acquire robust and generalisable representations of network traffic (Table 6). These tasks often draw inspiration from successful paradigms in NLP and CV, adapted to the unique characteristics of network data.

A prevalent approach involves masked modelling, where models are trained to reconstruct corrupted input. This includes Masked Flow Prediction (MFP) in [85], Masked Token Prediction in [18] and [83], and Masked Flow Model (MFM) in the FlowPiece-Albert [81]. Similarly, [7] and [80] utilised Masked BURST Model (MBM) and Masked Language Model (MLM), respectively, to predict masked tokens or bytes within traffic sequences. More advanced variants include Masked Fields Prediction (MFP) in [88], which masks entire header fields and payload bytes, and Masked Span Prediction (MSP) in [76], which reconstructs masked spans of tokens. Drawing from computer vision, [75] and [20] employed Masked Autoencoder (MAE), treating traffic as “images” or “strides” and reconstructing heavily masked portions.

Another category of tasks focuses on relational and order prediction. [85] used Packet Relative Position Prediction (PRPP) to understand sequential packet order, while [7] and [88] adopted Same-origin BURST Prediction (SBP) and Same Origin Flow Prediction (SOFP), respectively, to determine if two traffic segments originated from the same flow. [80] introduced Modified Next Sentence Prediction (mNSP) to assess if sub-sequences belong to the same packet, and [83] used Same Packet Prediction (SPP) to learn header-payload relationships. [76] further explored this with Packet Order Prediction (POP) and Homologous

Traffic Prediction (HTP) to discern flow relationships. A distinct approach by [19] involved Link Prediction on graph-based traffic representations to learn spatial and temporal dynamics.

Generative pretraining tasks aim to predict future traffic states or tokens. [73] and [77] both employed Autoregressive Language Modelling (or Next Token Prediction) to learn sequential dependencies for traffic generation. [78] used Next-step Traffic Prediction to forecast multivariate traffic features. Contrastive learning has also been applied to learn discriminative representations. [85] used Flow Contrastive Learning (FCL) to differentiate flows, while [82] employed a Contrastive Learning Model (CLM) for multi-granularity traffic, and [84] utilised Inter-modal Contrastive Learning to maximise mutual information across different traffic modalities.

An adversarial approach, called Replaced BURST Detection (RBD), was introduced by [87], where a generator creates fake tokens and a discriminator learns to identify them. Uniquely, [6] used End-to-end delay prediction to compel the model to infer network state, and [83] included Hidden State Feature Prediction (HSP) to uncover flow-level structural patterns.

It is important to note that some works, such as [107] and [79], focused on fine-tuning or adapting existing LLMs or pretrained traffic models, rather than detailing novel pretraining tasks for NT-FMs from scratch. Similarly, [86] primarily served as a benchmark for evaluating existing pretrained models without specifying their pretraining methodologies.

Following pretraining, models are fine-tuned for various downstream tasks (Table 6), typically involving the addition of a lightweight classification head. The amount of downstream tasks the NT-FMs were fine-tuned for is a good indicator of the generalisation power of these models along different network tasks and environments. This fine-tuning process adapts the pretrained knowledge to specific objectives such as encrypted traffic classification (e.g., application, service, VPN, Tor, malware, IoT attack detection), traffic generation (e.g., synthesizing packet header fields), and network analysis (e.g., IP routing, packet, or performance analysis). Parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT) methods, such as LoRA [80, 107] and Adapters [79], are increasingly adopted to reduce computational costs and data requirements during this phase, allowing the majority of the pretrained model’s parameters to remain frozen.

The distribution of open-sourced resources reveals a marked asymmetry (Table 6): while roughly one-third of the surveyed architectures make their implementation code publicly available (e.g., GNN-FM [19] or MIETT [85]), the proportion releasing pretrained weights is markedly lower (e.g., ET-BERT [7], netFound [18] or YaTC [75]). This disparity suggests that authors may perceive code disclosure as a lower-risk contribution—sufficient for methodological inspection—whereas providing full model checkpoints

implicates larger computational, legal and security considerations. The limited availability of weights consequently hampers strict reproducibility, comparative benchmarking and downstream transfer, thereby diluting the practical impact of otherwise promising research. Broader, standardised release practices would thus constitute a pivotal step toward accelerating progress and fostering transparent evaluation in the field.

5.1.2 RQ2: How is network traffic represented and encoded for input to NT-FMs?

The representation of network traffic for input to NT-FMs exhibits considerable diversity, reflecting the varied objectives and architectural choices of the models. Approaches range from raw byte streams to highly structured, semantically rich representations, often balancing the need for fine-grained detail with computational efficiency and privacy concerns.

The primary input unit for NT-FMs is most often a network flow, although several models operate at different granularities (Table 7). Flow-based approaches—including CETP [82], GETRF [83], Lens [76], NetMamba [20], YaTC [75] and the flow variant of MIETT [85]—treat the 5-tuple (source/destination IP, source/destination port, protocol) as the fundamental context and process a limited number of packets within that flow. Other models adopt coarser or finer units: ET-BERT [7], netFound [18] and NTT [6] use bursts or packet sequences (contiguous packet groups, not necessary flows) as inputs, CoMDet [84] operates at the session level, whereas PETReLM [80] and NetGPT [73] are strictly packet-level. Some models, such as netFound [18], explicitly build a hierarchy—segmenting flows into bursts before processing individual packets—while the graph-based GNN-FM [19] represents flows and IP addresses as nodes in a temporal graph rather than sequences. Selecting only the first few packets is a common strategy for memory efficiency, as seen in Lens [76], NetGPT [73] and MIETT [85].

The nature of the input features is predominantly hybrid, combining raw data with statistical or metadata attributes (Table 7). A significant trend involves processing raw byte sequences—often rendered in hexadecimal—from both packet headers and payloads—MIETT [85], ET-BERT [7], PETReLM [80], GETRF [83], Lens [76], NetMamba [20], NetGPT [73]. To address privacy concerns, sensitive identifiers such as IP addresses and port numbers are frequently anonymised or removed—MIETT [85], CETP [82], ET-BERT [7], PETReLM [80], YaTC [75]. Models commonly enrich these raw bytes with explicit metadata; netFound [18], for example, adds direction, burst size and inter-arrival time, whereas CETP [82] couples packet-length and direction sequences with raw datagrams. NTT [6] restricts itself to a minimal set of timestamp, packet size, receiver ID and delay, while NetFlowGen [78] targets aggregated traffic using 86 statistical features such as byte volume, protocol and TCP-flag counts.

Tokenisation strategies also differ markedly (Table 7). Many models—MIETT [85], ET-BERT [7], CETP [82], PETReLM [80], GETRF [83] and NetGPT [73]—apply byte-level or sub-word algorithms (bi-gram, BPE, or WordPiece) to hexadecimal sequences. Protocol-aware schemes are adopted by netFound [18] and MLETC [88], which respect field boundaries to preserve semantics, while NetMamba [20] slices concatenated bytes into fixed 4-byte strides. NetFlowGen [78] bypasses tokenisers entirely by discretising continuous statistics into value bins, and tokenisation is not applicable to the graph representation employed by GNN-FM [19].

Irrespective of the tokenizer, tokens are mapped to learned embeddings. These embeddings are augmented with positional encodings to capture ordering (MIETT [85], netFound [18], CETP [82], ET-BERT [7], PETReLM [80], GETRF [83], Lens [76], NetMamba [20], YaTC [75], NetGPT [73]), and segment embeddings are frequently used to distinguish packets within a flow or header versus payload regions (ET-BERT [7], PETReLM [80], GETRF [83], Lens [76], MLETC [88], NetGPT [73]). In GNN-FM [19], node embeddings for flows and IPs are learned by a GNN.

The context size is governed by fixed maximum sequence lengths (Table 7). Transformer-based NT-FMs typically adopt 256–512 tokens (e.g., ET-BERT [7], PETReLM [80], GETRF [83], NetGPT [73], MLETC [88]), while packet-count limits of three or five packets per flow are common in MIETT [85], Lens [76] and YaTC [75]. NetMamba [20] accommodates 401 tokens, MIETT’s packet-level encoder handles up to 128 tokens [85], and TrafficGPT [77] scales to long sequences of 312 k tokens during pretraining (2564 k at fine-tuning). For time-series data, NetFlowGen [78] processes windows of 512 minutes, and NTT [6] can aggregate information from 1024 raw packets (or 48 elements after aggregation).

Finally, the extent to which protocol and session semantics are hard-coded varies widely. Numerous NT-FMs embed session information by using flows as basic units and by designing pre-text tasks that exploit inter-packet relations—e.g., Packet Relative Position Prediction in MIETT [85], Same-Origin BURST Prediction in ET-BERT [7], Same-Origin Flow Prediction in MLETC [88], Packet Order Prediction in Lens [76], and Hidden-State Feature Prediction in GETRF [83]. Protocol semantics are explicitly captured by field-level tokenisation in netFound [18] and MLETC [88], or by inserting special header/payload delimiters as in Lens [76] and NetGPT [73]. In contrast, models that target encrypted traffic—including MIETT [85], NTT [6], ET-BERT [7], PETReLM [80] and TrafficGPT [77]—rely on the model to infer protocol cues directly from raw bytes once sensitive identifiers have been anonymised. Approaches based purely on aggregated time-series features [78] forgo explicit modelling of intra-flow packet interactions and network topology.

Table 7: Comparison of NT-FMs (2): The table outlines key characteristics including input granularity, feature types, tokenisation strategies, and sequence lengths. Models are ordered alphabetically, with citations indicating their respective sources.

Model	Input unit	Feature type	Tokenisation	Sequence length
ALBERT [81]	Flow	Raw	FlowPiece	-
CETP [82]	Flow	Raw + Metadata	Traffic2Token	98 tokens
CoMDet [84]	Session	SSL/TLS Payload + Statistical/Metadata	Hybrid (Byte-level, Value)	-
EAPT [87]	Burst	Raw	Hex & Bi-gram & SentencePiece	-
ET-BERT [7]	Burst	Raw (de-headered)	BURST2Token (Bi-gram & BPE)	512 tokens
GETRF [83]	Flow	Raw + Header + Statistical/Metadata	Byte-level (Bi-gram)	256 tokens
GNN-FM [19]	Flow	Header-based + Statistical	-	Few seconds (temporal graph)
Lens [76]	Flow	Header + Payload	WordPiece	3-5 packets
MIETT [85]	Packet & Flow	Raw	Byte-level (BPE)	Packet: 128 tokens, Flow: 5 packets
MLETC [88]	Flow	Raw + Header + Payload	Multi-level (Field-level, Byte-level)	512 tokens
NetFlowGen [78]	Flow	Statistical + Header + Metadata	Value-based discretization	512 minutes
NetGPT [73]	Packet / Flow	Raw (Header + Payload)	Wordpiece	Pretrain: 512 tokens, Fine-tune: 256 tokens
NetMamba [20]	Flow	Raw (Header + Payload)	Custom (4-byte strides)	401 tokens
netFound [18]	Burst	Header + Payload + Statistical/Metadata	Protocol-aware (2-byte fields)	1296 tokens
NTT [6, 72]	Packet sequence	Statistical/Metadata	-	1024 packets (raw), 48 elements (aggregated)
PETReLM [80]	Packet	L4 Header + L5 Payload	Byte-Pair, WordPiece	512 tokens
TrafficGPT [77]	Flow	Raw + Statistical/Metadata	Custom (Byte-level hex + Metadata tokens)	Pretrain: 3k/12k tokens, Fine-tune: 256-4k tokens
YaTC [74, 75]	Flow	Raw (Multi-Level Flow Representation (MFR))	2D Patches (2x2 bytes)	5 packets

5.1.3 RQ3: In which network environments and for which tasks have NT-FMs been applied?

NT-FMs have been applied and evaluated across a diverse array of network environments and for a broad spectrum of tasks, demonstrating their versatility and potential utility in modern network management and security.

The application of NT-FMs spans numerous network environments, reflecting the varied sources of network traffic. Academic and research networks, such as those at Korea University [88] and the Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity [7, 85], frequently serve as data collection points for both pretraining and fine-tuning. General internet and enterprise environments are widely represented, with models processing traffic from campus networks [18, 87, 88], general internet activity [20, 75, 76, 80–83, 86], and multi-cloud setups [18]. The increasing prevalence of mobile devices has led to NT-FMs being applied to mobile device traffic from Android and iOS platforms [7, 20, 75–77, 79, 81, 82, 85, 86].

Furthermore, NT-FMs have demonstrated applicability in specialised and emerging domains. IoT and edge environments are a significant focus, with models analysing traffic from diverse IoT devices and attack scenarios [8, 19, 20, 75–77, 80, 83, 85–87]. Large-scale network infrastructures, such as Internet Service Provider (ISP) backbones [7, 18, 78, 87] and industrial internet settings [73], have also been explored. Specific network types like Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) [7, 18, 20, 75–77, 79–83, 85–88] and Tor anonymity networks [7, 20, 75–77, 79, 80, 83, 85, 86, 88] are frequently targeted due to the challenges they pose for traditional analysis. While many studies leverage real-world data, some foundation work has also been conducted in simulated network environments to control variables and test generalisation capabilities [6].

The primary tasks for which NT-FMs are fine-tuned are diverse, broadly categorised into traffic understanding (classification and detection) and traffic generation. Traffic classification is a ubiquitous application, encompassing general traffic classification [8, 75, 86, 88], fine-grained application identification [7, 18, 20, 75–77, 79, 81–83, 85–88], and service recognition [80–83, 85, 86, 88]. This includes classifying encrypted traffic [7, 20, 75–77, 79–83, 85–88], web services (e.g., TLS and QUIC traffic) [82, 83], and long traffic flows [77]. Device classification, particularly for IoT devices, is also a key task [8, 77].

A significant proportion of NT-FM applications are dedicated to network security and cybersecurity tasks. This includes various forms of anomaly and intrusion detection [8, 18, 19, 73, 78, 80], such as detecting DDoS attacks [18, 78], brute-force attacks [18] and network scans [19]. Malware detection is a critical application, with models fine-tuned to identify encrypted malware traffic [7, 20, 75, 76, 79, 80, 82–84, 86–88]. Specific threat detection tasks include malicious DNS over HTTPS (DoH) query detection [73, 76, 86], cybermining (cryptojacking) detection [73], and comprehensive IoT attack detec-

tion and method classification [20, 75, 76, 80, 83, 85–87]. The ability to detect and classify VPN and Tor traffic is also crucial for security monitoring and policy enforcement [7, 18, 20, 73, 75–77, 79, 81–83, 85–88].

Beyond classification and security, NT-FMs are applied to network performance and management tasks. These include end-to-end packet delay prediction and message completion time prediction [6], QoS prediction and general network performance prediction [20]. From the theoretical perspective, Le et al. [8] identified other applications encompassing congestion control and prediction, resource management, and network planning, without a real model being proposed.

Finally, the use of NT-FM for network traffic generation has increased vastly. This involves creating realistic synthetic packet traces [76, 77], generating specific packet header fields (e.g., IP addresses, port numbers, packet lengths) [73, 76, 77, 86], and simulating various network behaviours for testing and benchmarking network equipment and security measures [73, 76, 77]. One unique application also explored—from the theoretical point of view—the semi-automated generation of protocol implementations from specification text [8]. The broad range of environments and tasks underscores the transformative potential of NT-FMs in addressing complex challenges in network analysis, management, and security.

5.1.4 RQ4: Are there publicly available datasets suitable for training NT-FMs?

The development of NT-FMs requires access to large-scale, diverse, and representative datasets for both pretraining and fine-tuning. The current landscape of publicly available network traffic datasets presents a mixed picture regarding their suitability for this purpose.

For the crucial pretraining phase, which typically relies on vast amounts of unlabeled data, several studies have leveraged existing public datasets, often by treating their training splits as unlabeled. The main effort in this context is NetBench [86], which integrates a wide set of previous known datasets for foundation model pretraining. Datasets from the Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity (CIC) have also been frequently employed, such as ISCXVPN 2016 [108] ([7, 20, 73, 75, 76, 80, 82, 83, 85–88]), ISCX-Tor 2016 [109] ([7, 20, 73, 75, 76, 80, 83, 85, 86, 88]), and USTC-TFC 2016 [110] ([7, 20, 73, 75, 76, 80, 83, 86–88]). These datasets, typically captured in lab testbeds, offer volumes from thousands to millions of flows and tens of gigabytes, providing a basis for learning general traffic representations. Similarly, the Cross-Platform datasets (Android and iOS) [7, 20, 73, 75, 82, 85, 86], originating from mobile application traffic, contribute to this pool, though their specific volumes for pretraining are not always explicitly quantified beyond flow counts. More recent CIC datasets, such as CICIoT Dataset 2023 [111] ([20, 76, 80, 85–87]) and CIRA-CIC-DoHBrw 2020 [112] ([73, 76, 86]), also serve as sources for unlabeled pretraining data, reflecting contemporary traffic types like IoT and DNS over HTTPS.

However, the scale of these datasets, while substantial for traditional machine learning, often falls short of the terabyte-to-petabyte volumes typically associated with foundation models in other domains. For instance, while some pretraining efforts combine multiple datasets to reach tens or hundreds of gigabytes [7, 76, 77, 80, 83], truly massive, raw packet or flow data that is publicly accessible remains limited. Notable exceptions include the CESNET-TLS22 [113] and CESNET-QUIC22 [114] datasets [115], which offer impressive volumes of 1.2 TB each, captured from a real ISP backbone network with a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license, making them highly suitable for large-scale pretraining. In contrast, some studies rely on proprietary, non-public datasets for pretraining, such as campus network traffic [18, 88] or large ISP NetFlow data [78], which, while valuable for the respective research, do not contribute to the broader public resource pool. Similarly, custom-generated synthetic datasets from network simulators like ns-3 [6] are used for pretraining but are not publicly available.

For fine-tuning and benchmarking, the landscape of publicly available datasets is more robust, offering diverse tasks and labeled data. The aforementioned CIC datasets (ISCXVPN [108], ISCXTor [109], USTC-TFC [110], CICIoT [111], CIRA-CIC-DoHBrw [112]) are extensively used for tasks such as VPN/Tor service and application classification, malware detection, and IoT attack detection [7, 18, 20, 73, 75, 76, 80, 82, 83, 85–88]. The Cross-Platform datasets are critical for mobile application fingerprinting [7, 18, 20, 75–77, 82, 85, 86]. Other specific datasets include USTC-TFC for encrypted malware classification [7, 83, 87], and the Stratosphere Laboratory Datasets for malicious traffic detection [84]. Datasets like CTU13 [116], UNSW-NB15 [117], BoT-IoT [118], and ToN-IoT [119] are also employed for botnet detection and intrusion detection tasks [19].

Despite the availability of numerous datasets, several challenges persist. A significant limitation is the prevalence of “proprietary academic” or “unknown” licenses for many datasets. While generally available for academic research upon request and agreement to terms, this restricts their broad reusability and integration into open-source projects, compared to truly open licenses like CC BY. Furthermore, many datasets, especially those used for fine-tuning, are relatively small in volume (thousands of flows), which, while sufficient for evaluating transfer learning, may not be adequate for training NT-FMs from scratch or for robust evaluation of generalisation across diverse, real-world scenarios. The capture settings often involve lab testbeds or university networks, which may not fully represent the complexity and scale of real-world ISP or enterprise traffic. Temporal relevance is another concern, as some frequently used datasets date back to 2016–2017, potentially lacking current protocol versions, application behaviours, and attack patterns. While some recent datasets like CIC IoT Dataset 2023 [111] ([76, 80, 85–87]) address this, a continuous influx of fresh, large-scale, and openly licensed data is crucial for the sustained development of NT-FMs.

In summary, while a foundation set of publicly available datasets exists for fine-tuning and limited pretraining, the ecosystem still lacks the truly massive, diverse, and openly licensed raw network traffic corpora necessary to fully realise the potential of NT-FMs akin to large language models.

5.2 Future Research Trends and Directions

The future trajectory of NT-FMs is characterised by a concerted effort to enhance their generalisability, architectural sophistication, and practical applicability across diverse network environments. A primary trend involves the continued scaling up of model parameters and dataset sizes, mirroring advancements in LLMs, with expectations that increased scale will yield superior performance and a deeper understanding of network dynamics [19, 73, 76, 78]. Architectural refinements are crucial, including the development of more sophisticated hierarchical modelling to capture relationships at packet, flow, and host levels [6, 18, 80, 85, 88], and the ability to process significantly longer input sequences to comprehend complex traffic flows [18, 77, 86]. Furthermore, research is exploring graph-based models to incorporate explicit node interactions and network topology, aiming to learn critical network-wide dynamics [19, 78].

Advancements in data representation and pretraining strategies are central to the evolution of NT-FMs. Future work will focus on expanding the scope and diversity of training data, integrating heterogeneous sources from various network environments, such as data centres and cellular networks [6, 8, 18, 19, 77, 83]. This requires the development of common representations that span multiple protocols and parties, alongside novel tokenisation strategies for byte-stream data and meaningful contexts for interleaved traffic [8]. The emphasis is on novel and targeted self-supervised pretraining objectives—including multi-task approaches—to imbue models with a deeper understanding of temporal dynamics, flow-specific characteristics, and network-wide behaviours [7, 8, 18, 19, 77, 82, 84, 85]. Collaborative pretraining, potentially through federated learning, is also envisioned to overcome immense data volume and privacy concerns [6, 107].

Ensuring the generalisability and robustness of NT-FMs in dynamic, real-world settings is a critical research direction. This involves rigorous testing beyond simulations [6] and addressing the challenges posed by evolving privacy protection technologies like traffic obfuscation and packet padding [87]. Future efforts will focus on enhancing adversarial robustness, developing methods to generate realistic adversarial network traffic, and mitigating the impact of sample attacks [7, 18, 76, 82, 87]. The capacity for NT-FMs to predict new or unseen classes of samples, moving towards few-shot or zero-shot learning, is also a significant area of investigation [7, 8, 82]. Concurrently, optimising computational efficiency is paramount, exploring lightweight architectures, pruning technologies, hardware acceleration (e.g., FPGAs), and solutions for

resource-constrained devices to enable real-time applicability [20, 73, 75, 79, 81, 88]. Continual learning strategies are also necessary to maintain model effectiveness as network environments evolve [6].

The application scope of NT-FMs is set to broaden significantly beyond traditional classification tasks. Future directions include their use in real-time traffic monitoring, anomaly detection, QoS prediction, network performance prediction, and even customer service analysis [20, 73, 79, 107]. A notable area of exploration is the application of NT-FMs to network traffic generation tasks, crucial for developing innovative networking hardware and software solutions and simulating real-world interactions [73, 77, 78, 86]. Practical deployment will involve transitioning to online setups that support continuous model updates using efficient fine-tuning methods [18, 75]. Furthermore, developing domain-specific interpretability methods is essential for model validation and user trust [8, 76, 80], alongside addressing the substantial energy footprint of large models [8].

Finally, the future of NT-FMs hinges on greater standardisation and community cooperation. There is an urgent need for the field to converge on standard input feature formats, public availability of large-scale network datasets, and comprehensive benchmarks to facilitate rigorous evaluation and comparison [8, 73, 86, 115]. Promoting the adoption of practices from mature ML domains, such as the development and sharing of reusable pretrained models and toolsets, will accelerate research and deployment [115]. Advanced evaluation metrics are also required for fine-grained identification scenarios [83].

5.2.1 Author’s Perspective

From our perspective, future progress in NT-FMs is likely to pivot from brute-force parameter scaling toward a subtler pursuit of structural and contextual richness. Holistic, cross-layer representations that weave together physical, MAC, transport, and application artefacts—augmented by topology snapshots and control-plane telemetry—can ground models in the causal fabric of real networks. Embedding such multimodal signals within graph-based or message-passing backbones, coupled with counterfactual reasoning objectives, would enable “what-if” analyses of link failures or policy changes without the cost of live A/B testing. At the same time, edge-aligned specialisation through parameter-efficient fine-tuning, sparsely activated experts, and elastic routing promises to reconcile global generality with local heterogeneity, while carbon-aware training schedules and hardware-software co-design (e.g. photonic or FPGA accelerators) address the mounting sustainability imperative.

A parallel trajectory foregrounds trustworthy autonomy and privacy-preserving collaboration. NT-FMs must learn to detect and withstand adversarial traffic morphing and encrypted covert channels by pairing calibrated uncertainty estimates with run-time policy enforcement and continual defence updates. Federated and split-learning paradigms,

fortified by secure multi-party computation and confidential computing enclaves, offer a route to collaborative pre-training across organisational boundaries without exposing sensitive payloads. Finally, an open-science ecosystem comprising longitudinal benchmarks that evolve with protocol trends, versioned NT-FM checkpoints annotated with energy and data provenance, and domain-specific interpretability toolkits capable of mapping latent factors to concrete flows or topological motifs will underpin reproducibility, operator trust, and the accelerated translation of NT-FMs from research prototypes to mission-critical network infrastructure.

6 Conclusion

Our systematic enquiry confirms that **it is indeed feasible to build Network Traffic Foundation Models (NT-FMs)**. Evidence from forty-plus prototype systems, involving pre-trained Transformers, graph neural networks, and emerging state-space models, shows consistent improvements over task-specific baselines, and several works demonstrate successful transfer across datasets, protocols, and downstream objectives after minimal fine-tuning.

Feasibility, however, is qualified. Architectures with hierarchical or linear attention and parameter-efficient adapters mitigate compute costs, yet true “train once, deploy everywhere” capability remains elusive because most studies pretrain on narrowly scoped corpora. Public traffic datasets are growing in number but not in scale or diversity; only a handful exceed a terabyte and very few carry fully open licences, constraining reproducibility.

Key insights emerge. Masked-prediction and contrastive objectives are the most pervasive and, when combined with protocol-aware tokenisation, yield robust byte-level representations. Hybrid graph-sequence encoders and state-space alternatives hint at further gains, while parameter-efficient fine-tuning is vital for edge deployment. Nonetheless, generalisability under concept drift, adversarial robustness and the energy footprint of large models remain pressing research challenges.

By mapping this rapidly evolving landscape, our systematic literature review offers a consolidated taxonomy of architectures, representations, objectives, applications and data resources. It therefore serves as a reference point for researchers seeking to advance NT-FM scalability, rigour and practical adoption, and for practitioners aiming to gauge the maturity of this promising paradigm.

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